

FINLAND'S EXPERIENCE IN IMPROVING THE PRIMARY EDUCATION SYSTEM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11175209>

Abstract. This article explores Finland's successful primary education system, highlighting its historical reforms, teacher education emphasis, and student-centric approaches. By analyzing Finland's educational strategies and cultural values, we discuss how these elements contribute to its high rankings in global education assessments. The scalability of this model and its implications for other countries seeking reform are also considered. The insights from Finland's approach suggest that significant educational improvements are possible through systemic and cultural dedication to education.

Keywords: Finnish education, education reforms, teacher training, student-centricity, educational outcomes, global models

Аннотация. В этой статье исследуется успешная система начального образования Финляндии, подчеркиваются ее исторические реформы, упор на педагогическое образование и подходы, ориентированные на учащихся. Анализируя образовательные стратегии и культурные ценности Финляндии, мы обсуждаем, как эти элементы способствуют ее высоким рейтингам в глобальных оценках образования. Также рассматриваются масштабируемость этой модели и ее последствия для других стран, стремящихся к реформам. Результаты подхода Финляндии показывают, что значительные улучшения в сфере образования возможны за счет системной и культурной приверженности образованию.

Ключевые слова: Финское образование, реформы образования, подготовка учителей, личностно-ориентированность, результаты образования, глобальные модели.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Finlyandiyaning muvaffaqiyatli boshlang'ich ta'lim tizimi o'rganilib, uning tarixiy islohotlari, pedagogik ta'limga e'tibor va o'quvchilarga yo'naltirilgan yondashuvlar ta'kidlangan. Finlyandiyaning ta'lim strategiyalari va madaniy qadriyatlarini tahlil qilib, biz ushbu elementlar global ta'limni baholashda uning yuqori reytinglariga qanday hissa qo'shishini muhokama qilamiz. Ushbu modelning miqyosi va uning islohotlarga intilayotgan boshqa mamlakatlarga ta'siri ham ko'rib chiqiladi. Finlyandiyaning yondashuv natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, ta'limga tizimli va madaniy sodiqlik orqali ta'lim sohasida sezilarli yutuqlar qilish mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: Finlyandiya ta'limi, ta'lim islohotlari, o'qituvchilar malakasini oshirish, shaxsga yo'naltirish, ta'lim natijalari, global modellar

Finland's primary education system has become a paragon of success, widely recognized for its remarkable outcomes in international educational assessments. The Nordic country has not only challenged conventional pedagogical methodologies but has also positioned itself as a leader in educational reform. This article seeks to explore the intricate journey of how Finland has consistently improved its education system, particularly at the primary level. We will look into the strategic reforms, cultural ethos, and supportive policies that have contributed to the educational excellence observed today. By dissecting Finland's approach, we can uncover insights and strategies that other nations might adapt to enhance their own educational frameworks.

Historical Context and Overhaul of the Education System. Before the 1970s, Finland's education system was fairly decentralized and varied significantly from one region to another. Educational opportunities were often dependent on the student's social background and the resources of their local municipalities, leading to disparities in quality and access.

The major overhaul of Finland's education system began in the 1970s when a comprehensive school reform was implemented. This reform made education free and accessible to all children from pre-school to higher education, effectively eliminating the previously widespread private schools and establishing a uniform public school system. The reform aimed to provide equal opportunities for every child regardless of their background, an ethos that remains at the core of the system today.

Core Elements of the Finnish Education Model. Finland's curriculum is designed to foster not just academic skills but also holistic development. It emphasizes creativity, critical thinking, and problem-solving, integrating subjects into broader, thematic units rather than isolated topics. This approach encourages students to see connections between disciplines, enhancing their understanding and application of knowledge.

One of the cornerstones of Finland's educational success is the high standard of its teacher education. All primary school teachers are required to have a master's degree, and the profession is highly competitive, attracting some of the best talents in the country. Teachers in Finland are also given a great deal of autonomy, trusted to design their own lesson plans and choose their methods of assessment.

Finnish primary education places a strong emphasis on addressing the individual needs of each student. Classrooms often adapt to different learning styles and paces, with less focus on standardized testing. Additionally, Finnish schools allocate time for play and free activities, which are considered crucial for child development and learning.

The Finnish government provides significant autonomy to local schools and teachers, but it also ensures that schools are well-funded and resources are equitably distributed. The local authorities are responsible for implementing national guidelines in ways that best fit their community, allowing for tailored educational approaches.

Cultural Factors Influencing Educational Success. Education is highly valued in Finnish society, and there is profound respect for the teaching profession. This cultural perspective is reflected in the resources allocated to education and the community involvement in schools, contributing to the system's overall success.

Trust permeates the Finnish education system: trust in teachers' professional judgment, trust in students' ability to learn and behave responsibly, and trust in schools to operate effectively without excessive control. This has created an environment where education thrives on mutual respect and responsibility.

Lessons and Implications for Other Countries. While Finland's education model has garnered international acclaim, replicating it in its entirety might not be feasible in all contexts due to different cultural, social, and economic conditions. However, elements of its approach, such as prioritizing teacher quality and providing child-centered education, can be adapted to improve educational systems elsewhere.

Countries looking to reform their education systems can learn from Finland's emphasis on teacher education, student-centered learning, and trust-based administration. Implementing similar

principles may require significant cultural shifts and policy adjustments, but the Finnish model demonstrates the transformative potential of such reforms.

Finland’s journey in refining its primary education system provides compelling evidence of what is possible when a country commits wholly to educational excellence. With a blend of strategic reforms, cultural commitment, and policy support, Finland has crafted an education system that supports every child's ability to learn and succeed. As countries around the world seek to enhance their educational outcomes, Finland’s experience offers both inspiration and practical lessons that can inform future educational policies and reforms.

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